

When Max Müller died his whole library went to Tokyo, and not to Oxford. However, a group of friends and admirers gathered together enough money to set up a small fund in Oxford, named after Max Müller, that his memory might be materially preserved there. This fund was to be used to foster ties with India and to promote things Indian.

In 1907 Professor A.A. Macdonell set off for India with £100 of this fund in order to buy manuscripts for the Bodleian Library. When he arrived in Benares, he reported,

'I was put in communication by Mahāmahopādhyāya Haraprasād Śāstrī, when I arrived at Benares, with a Brahmin possessing a large library. When I had carefully examined the MSS submitted to me by the Pandit, I chose and purchased those described in the present catalogue.... I contributed a summary account of the collection to the Royal Asiatic Society's Journal for 1910, pp. 829-30.'²

Now Macdonell had obviously been impressed by the collection he had seen in Benares, for on his return to England he immediately alerted the Bodleian to this valuable find and,³

'At the same time [1908] Professor Macdonell drew the attention of the curators to the desirability of acquiring en bloc the extensive library from which he had made his selection [of the 100 sanskrit MSS described by T. Gambier-Parry in his 1922 catalogue]. On being informed that here was a store that would form a most welcome addition to the Bodleian's treasures, Lord Curzon, at that time Chancellor of the University, prevailed upon the Maharajah Sir Chandra Shum Shere, Prime Minister of Nepal, to buy the collection and present it in 1909 to Oxford.

The Chandra Shum Shere manuscripts, for so they are called in memory of their donor, were reckoned as no fewer than 6330 in number, and could claim to be the largest collection of Indian manuscripts ever brought to England. Binding, towards which the Common University Fund made a grant of £1000, has brought them into the compass of 2,152 volumes. Even by that computation their acquisition has more than doubled the size of the Bodleian Sanskrit collection, which in 1905 totalled 1,321 manuscripts. None are of high antiquity, but every branch of Sanskrit literature is represented in them, as may be seen from the still unpublished catalogue compiled by Mr Gambier-Parry.'

That catalogue was to remain unpublished for nearly a century. It is still not published.

Together with the MSS, when they arrived in 1909, came a handlist giving for each MS a number, title, sometimes an author and sometimes the number of folios.⁴ This handlist, written in Devanāgarī

script, bears the stamp of the Bodleian, dated 5.11.1909. The name of the list's owner is Aśu^oṣh Tārkatīrtha and he did, or had done, a thorough and systematic list, brief though it is.⁵ The name Haraprasād Śāstrin is also written on the first page, but it has been crossed out. The question stands as to whether this Aśu^oṣh Tārkatīrtha is the same person as the 'Benares Pundit' from whom the collection was purchased. It seems likely.

This list came into the hands of T. Gambier-Parry⁶, then ^Kkeeper of Oriental Books, and he used it as the basis for his own initial work on the collection. The first thing he must have done was to group the MSS into size categories (a-g) and subjects and give them a new set of numbers.⁷ The MSS were then bound.⁸ Aśu^oṣh Tārkatīrtha's numbers ran from 1 to 6330.⁹ Gambier-Parry's numbers applied to the 2,152 bound volumes, which often contain more than one MS. These individual MSS are referred to by brackets after Gambier-Parry's number. eg: b.61(2). Gambier-Parry annotated Aśu^oṣh Tārkatīrtha's handlist, writing the new MS volume number against each entry and making occasional corrections.

The high quality and thoroughness of Gambier-Parry's work should here be emphasised, especially considering his constant illness (lungs) which closed in on him even more towards the end of his life, when this cataloguing was done. He did a very great deal of initial sorting out, often recombining MS fragments and so on. Once the MSS were bound he foliated them in pencil and wrote on the inside covers of the volumes the names and original numbers of the MSS contained in each volume. At some time during the process he prepared a small handbook giving the volume numbers and a very rough guide to what MSS were in each volume.¹⁰ eg: 'd.59 : 9 miscel. Upanishads.' Where there was only one MS in the bound volume he gave its title briefly. These entries seem to correspond to what is written on the spines of the bound volumes.

The next step was to start the cataloguing proper. Gambier-Parry had a number of index cards printed specially for this collection and assigned one card to each individual MS. On each card he recorded the following:

- i) The MS number. eg: d.250(2)
- ii) Title.
- iii) Author.
- iv) Commentary.
- v) Subject. eg: grammar, ritual, astronomy etc.
- vi) Notes. This sometimes went as far as including a brief incipit.
- vii) Number of leaves.
- ix) Script.
- x) Number of lines a page.

His entries were, as far as I may judge, accurate and full. Sometimes extra notes were written on the backs of the cards and also, occasionally, on the inside cover of the MSS volume itself, when the text was particularly disarranged. eg: d.218

These cards are at present in numerical order of press-mark. But at one stage Gambier-Parry must have arranged them alphabetically, for he began writing an alphabetical title-index to the collection, incorporating all the information he had recorded on the cards.

This list continues up to śūdrasaṃskāra in the Sanskrit alphabet and then Gambier-Parry's writing breaks off. It is assumed that this was because of the onset of the long illness which was, in February 1935, to end his life. He died only five days after his own mother, just two days after his fifty-second birthday.¹¹

Now a new figure came onto the scene. This was Professor Johnston, Boden Professor of Sanskrit from 1937 to 1942.¹² He found the point to which Gambier-Parry had progressed and took up the job of completing the alphabetical index. But first of all he returned to the MSS themselves and compared each one with Gambier-Parry's cards. In nearly every case he added further details, foliations of sections, names of scribes, etc. After recording this on the cards he turned to the index and wrote in all his supplementations. Next, he continued the list where Gambier-Parry had left off, and completed it. The latter part of the list (p.327ff.) has sections on the MSS in modern Indian languages; Hindī (166MSS), Mārāthī (93MSS), bengālī (17MSS), Gujarāti (15MSS), Panjābi (20MSS), Kashmīri (1MS), Nepālī (1MS) and an unclassified section (27MSS) followed by further notes on 19 of the Panjābi MSS.

From this time until 1977 the work of cataloguing the collection was at a total standstill.¹³ Not only that; the situation actually regressed, because the cards and the alphabetical index fell into oblivion. Their value was forgotten. Scholars wishing to find out what was in this vast collection were offered just the small handbook of Gambier-Parry, with its virtually meaningless entries. It was, after all, never meant to be more than a record of the volumes' spine notes, one suspects. And while a scholar in the reading room might be wrestling with '12 miscellaneous works of grammar and logic', the complete alphabetical index was quietly gathering dust in a back room. Several factors brought this situation about, and no fingers can, or need, be pointed. Among other reasons, the index, it was felt by those who actually knew it existed, was not a finished enough product to be on general view to readers.

The next time, after Professor Johnston, that the original cards were handled was during the two years preceding the summer of 1976.

In this period a typist who had been employed by the Library was given the cards and asked to type them out on a free-lance basis. She was not a sanskritist, and Gambier-Parry's and Johnston's writing is, in all fairness, often far from clear, so a number of mistakes appeared on the two sets of typed cards that were produced. A number of the details noted on the original cards were omitted. The result of this work was that in 1976 the Library had two sets of typed cards, imperfectly reproduced from the original hand written cards; ~~a swinging watch for the investigator to stare at.~~ One of these sets was arranged in numerical order of press-mark, in drawers, with markers showing Gambier-Parry's subject classification through the sections of MSS in Devanāgarī script. The large numbers of MSS in Bengāli, Telugu, Śārada and other scripts were labelled 'miscellaneous'. It should be said here that this move, inadequate though it was, was at least a move in the right direction. It was a step towards making the contents of the collection visible.¹⁴

In 1977 Professor David Pingree of Brown University, USA, came to Oxford to gather materials for his Census of the Exact Sciences in Sanskrit (CESS). He was given the handbook only. Working from this he identified 500 astronomical texts and examined them briefly, leaving with the Library a handlist of them.¹⁵ Professor Pingree's handlist is very brief, giving just the author, title and number of folios for each MS. However, the dates of the authors are often included, and he has worked out the very numerous colphons, thus often giving the exact day on which the MS was completed. This kind of information is only his to offer. The list as it stands should really be viewed in the larger context of Professor Pingree's CESS.

Since Professor Pingree's visit in 1977, interest in the collection has been reawakened by the public statement of its importance made by Professor Gombrich in his inaugural lecture (Oct.1977). The new Librarian of the Indian Institute, Mr. J. Katz, is fully alive to the importance of issuing a descriptive catalogue of this huge collection, but this is inevitably a long job. In the meantime it is hoped that specialists in the various Śāstras (disciplines) can be attracted to Oxford and asked to deal with that part of the collection which is of direct interest to them. In this way it may be possible to produce a series of subject catalogues for the collection, which could at some later stage be combined into a union catalogue.

pīṣṭapeṣaṇanivāranārtham likhitam

D. Wujastyk, March 1978

Notes

1. T.R. Gambier-Parry, A Catalogue of the Sanskrit Manuscripts Purchased for the Administrators of the Max Müller Memorial Fund (Oxford, 1922), p.iii.
2. This article contains no details about the acquisition of the MSS, but characterises the most important of them.
3. E. Craster, History of the Bodleian Library 1845-1945 (Oxford, 1952), p. 219.
4. Now available at press-mark MS. CSS. e.272-277. *Chandra Shum Shere*
5. A crossed out note, a few pages after the end of the list in e.277, says that the list was written by one Narapati Jayacaryyā.
6. b. 1883 , d. 1935.
7. Prof. Pingree has detected a subject grouping even in the number sequence assigned by Áśuṭoṣh Tārkatīrtha. eg: 2800-3400 = Jyotiṣa. But it is very rough.
8. cf. Gambier-Parry's personal file, 'T. Gambier-Parry. Chief work.' This gives 1919 as the terminus ad quem for the binding.
9. The last page of the list has been prepared to take entries 6331-6340, but they were never made. Does part of this library still remain in Benares?
10. Available in the reading room on request. It has on its spine, 'MSS Chandra Shum Shere 75^o.'
11. A letter from A.A.Macdonell dated Nov. 1927 speaks of the catalogue as completed. cf. Gambier-Parry's personal file.
12. Identified by his handwriting.
13. Professor ^{V.}Raghavan saw the collection in 1954, but his notes have never been available at Oxford. Nor is there any mention of the collection in NCC.
14. More recently a tertiary-order operation was started; the comparison of the written with the typed cards, and the attempt at correction. This huge and questionable job was indefinitely suspended by Mr J. Katz.
15. Press mark Z. Cat. 419.